

BROADBAND DIELECTRIC SPECTRA AND MICROWAVE ABSORBING / SHIELDING EFFICIENCY OF DIELECTRIC-CONDUCTOR NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

We present analysis of the microwave shielding and absorption efficiency of some polymer-based dielectric-conductor nanocomposites of a) poly(ethylene terephthalate) and multiwalled carbon nanotubes; b) epoxy resin and magnetic metal (Ni and Fe) nanoparticles; c) variously conducting polyaniline pellets (conducting, semi-conducting and non-conducting) with nano-inhomogeneous conductivity due to their semi-crystalline structure. The analysis is based on the experimentally studied broadband spectra of complex dielectric permittivity (for some composites, from 0.1 mHz to 1 THz). In the case of epoxy resin – metal composites, spectra of the complex magnetic permeability were additionally measured in the frequency range from 1 MHz to 3 GHz. The complex permittivity and permeability spectra were used for calculation of shielding efficiency (SE) and microwave absorption (MA) of the composites in the microwave and THz ranges in dependence on the composition, layer thickness and frequency. SE up to 35 dB and MA up to 30 dB were shown to be achieved in narrow and relatively broad bands between 300 MHz and 1 THz for some composite layers. The compositions and frequency range optimal for shielding and absorption applications are discussed. Broadband dielectric spectroscopy is considered as an effective tool for the study and development of microwave shielding and absorbing composite materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Dielectric-conductor composites belong to effective absorbing and shielding materials which are widely used in electronics and telecommunications, military and civilian microwave (MW) techniques [1,2,3]. Electrically inhomogeneous structure of the dielectric-conductor composites is responsible for the dielectric dispersion in a very broad frequency range, including MW frequencies [4-7] and consequently results in a high level of their electromagnetic (EM) field absorption at high, MW and even THz frequencies.

Microwave absorbing and shielding properties of materials are usually estimated in two ways [1,2,8,9]. The first one is based on direct experimental measurements of reflection and transmission coefficients of the material layer or multilayer structure in free space or transmission line (waveguide). But for the free space microwave measurements, big samples are required. The waveguide measurements can be performed with smaller samples, but usually in the relatively narrow frequency range. These problems limit practical application of the direct experimental measurements.

The second way is simulations, model calculations based on the measured (usually, at a single frequency) or a priori taken values of dielectric permittivity and losses (or conductivity). Consequently, dielectric dispersion is not accounted. But composite materials (especially dielectric-conductor composites) are characterized the strong frequency dependence of their dielectric

parameters. It can lead to essential disagreement of the results of such simulations with real absorbing or shielding properties of the material. Correct simulations should be based on the experimentally measured spectra of the complex dielectric permittivity $\varepsilon^*(f) = \varepsilon'(f) - i\varepsilon''(f)$ consisting of the frequency dependences of permittivity $\varepsilon'(f)$ and loss $\varepsilon''(f)$. The last approach was successfully applied (see [10,11] for instance), even if the dielectric spectra were measured in the relatively narrow frequency range, less than one decade of frequency.

We propose combination of the experimental and simulation approaches and present analysis of shielding and absorption efficiency of composites based on the experimentally measured broadband dielectric spectra, including high frequency, MW and THz ranges. For our analysis, we use dielectric spectra of several polymer-based dielectric-conductor nanocomposites:

a) Composites of poly(ethylene terephthalate) and multiwalled carbon nanotubes (PET-xCNT, $x = 0-3$ vol.% is the fraction of carbon nanotubes). Their dielectric spectra were recently studied in a very broad frequency range up to 1 THz [4].

b) Epoxy resin and magnetic metal nanoparticles (epoxy-xNi and epoxy-xFe, $x = 0-40$ vol.% is the fraction of Ni or Fe nanoparticles). In this case, we use the spectra of both complex dielectric permittivity and magnetic permeability $\mu^*(f) = \mu'(f) - i\mu''(f)$ measured in the frequency range from 1 MHz to 3 GHz [12-14].

c) Various conducting polyaniline pellets (conducting c-PANI, semi-conducting sc-PANI and non-conducting nc-PANI). PANI has nano-inhomogeneous conductivity due to its semi-crystalline structure, where the crystalline nanoregions (~ 10 nm) are more conducting than the amorphous ones, and also due to the presence of oligomers and interrupted chains in the less-conducting PANI forms. Their dielectric spectra were studied in a broad frequency range up to 1 THz [6].

2 DIELECTRIC AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES

2.1 Dielectric spectra of PET-CNT composites

Dielectric dispersion in the high-frequency range was observed for all PET-CNT compositions (Fig. 1). It was shown that in addition to the *dc* conductivity of percolated CNT clusters, the *ac* conductivity of CNT in the finite clusters contributes to the dielectric spectra [4]. The *ac* conductivity increases with frequency and culminates in the THz range for all compositions, achieving ~ 4 S/cm at 1 THz. The percolation threshold revealed at $x_c \sim 0.07$ vol.% is one of the lowest observed in the melt-processed polymer composites. The *dc* and *ac* conductivity, as well as dielectric spectra of composites can be effectively controlled by the change of CNT concentration. The low percolation threshold and ability of modification of their MW dielectric properties make PET-CNT composites attractive for EM applications.

Dielectric spectra of several PET-CNT composites were modeled below the percolation threshold by a set of phenomenological Cole-Cole relaxations, one THz oscillator and a Drude term describing the low-frequency conductivity above the electrical percolation threshold [4,6]. The resulting fitted spectra for selected compositions are shown in Fig. 1 together with the experimental ones.

2.2 Dielectric and magnetic spectra of epoxy-Ni and epoxy-Fe composites

Dielectric spectra of the epoxy-Fe and epoxy-Ni composites with different concentrations of nanosized metallic particles are presented in Figures 2 and 3. The power-law dispersion of permittivity characterizes response in the high-frequency and MW ranges for all studied composites. The spectra are similar to that of the composites with carbon nanoparticles and nanotubes [4] and the power-law dispersion was attributed to the *ac* conductivity in finite metal clusters (i.e., to the dynamics of the charge carriers in the fractal conducting network) and inter-cluster polarization of insulating matrix [12].

Increase in the metal content generally results in increase in the effective dielectric permittivity, loss and conductivity of the composite at all frequencies. MW *ac* conductivity ($10^8 - 10^{10}$ Hz) of the studied metal-dielectric composites varies in a broad range (from 10^{-7} S/cm to 1 S/cm) and can be controlled by changing the metallic nanoparticle concentration [12]. This is very important and promising for their tentative application as MW absorbing or shielding materials.

Figure 1: Frequency dependences of dielectric permittivity (ϵ') and loss (ϵ'') of PET-CNT composites. Symbols denote experimental points, lines are phenomenological fits.

Figure 2 (on the left): Frequency dependences of (a) dielectric permittivity and (b) loss of the epoxy-Fe composites.

Figure 3 (on the right): Frequency dependences of (a) dielectric permittivity and (b) loss of the epoxy-Ni composites.

Additional useful contribution to the high-frequency absorbing or shielding efficiency of the studied composites could arise from magnetic properties of the Ni and Fe nanoparticles. Experimentally measured spectra of the real μ' and imaginary μ'' parts of the complex magnetic permeability of the epoxy-Fe and epoxy-Ni composites [13,14] are presented in Figures 4 and 5. For all studied compositions, magnetic dispersion was observed in the frequency range 1 MHz – 3 GHz. The increase in concentration of ferromagnetic inclusions leads to an increase in the values of magnetic permeability and losses at all frequencies. For the epoxy-Fe composites, maximum of the magnetic loss μ'' is observed between 10 MHz and 100 MHz. In the case of epoxy-Ni composites, the main magnetic-loss maximum takes place above 3 GHz, i.e. above our experimental range. Additionally, the local maximum is observed between 100 MHz and 1 GHz. Then, the magnetic absorption band of epoxy-Ni composites is shifted towards higher frequencies compared to that of the epoxy-Fe composites.

High level of both dielectric and magnetic losses of the epoxy-Fe and epoxy-Ni composites observed in the high-frequency and MW ranges (see Figs. 2-5) is a positive feature for absorbing / shielding materials.

Figure 4 (on the left): Frequency dependence of (a) real and (b) imaginary parts of complex magnetic permeability of the epoxy-Fe composites.

Figure 5 (on the right): Frequency dependence of (a) real and (b) imaginary parts of complex magnetic permeability of the epoxy-Ni composites.

2.3 Dielectric spectra of variously conducting PANI

Dielectric and *ac* conductivity spectra of the variously conducting PANI pellets show a standard behavior of nano-inhomogeneous or composite conductors with the low-frequency plateau of conductivity and dielectric dispersion in a broad frequency range [6]. Their *dc* conductivity corresponding to the low-frequency plateau level vary from $\sim 10^{-12}$ S/cm for nc-PANI to $\sim 10^{-5}$ S/cm for sc-PANI and ~ 1 S/cm for c-PANI. Dielectric spectra of PANI were modeled similar to that of the PET-CNT composites by a set of phenomenological Cole-Cole relaxations, one overdamped THz

oscillator and a Drude term describing the low-frequency conductivity [6]. We use the resulting fitted spectra for calculations of PANI shielding and absorption efficiency.

3 MODEL CALCULATIONS OF SHIELDING AND ABSORPTION EFFICIENCY

To estimate the shielding and absorption properties, we relate them to the dielectric and magnetic spectra of composites (described in the Section 2) by analysis of EM wave interaction with the composite layer (absorber) in free space. Two model configurations (Fig. 6) were analyzed: a) EM wave transmission through a single layer; b) EM wave reflection from the layer backed by a perfect electric conductor. The EM wave is considered to be normally incident. The characteristic impedance Z_2 and propagation constant γ of the absorber are defined by the complex dielectric permittivity and magnetic permeability of a composite [2,8,9]:

$$Z_2 = Z_0 \sqrt{\frac{\mu^*}{\varepsilon^*}}, \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{i\omega\sqrt{\mu^*\varepsilon^*}}{c}, \quad (2)$$

where $Z_0 = 377$ Ohm is the characteristic impedance of the free space and c is the speed of light in free space. The characteristic impedances Z_1 and Z_3 of the semi-infinite media are equal to Z_0 in the case of free space or air. Considering the metal plate as a perfect electric conductor, we suppose $Z_3 = 0$ [8] in the case of Fig. 6b. Then the input wave impedance Z_{in} of the analyzed structures at the surface of the absorber can be defined, according to the transmission line theory [2,9], as

$$Z_{in} = Z_2 \frac{Z_3 \cosh(\gamma d) + Z_2 \sinh(\gamma d)}{Z_2 \cosh(\gamma d) + Z_3 \sinh(\gamma d)}, \quad (3)$$

where d is the thickness of the absorber layer.

Figure 6: Scheme of the EM wave interaction with the composite material (absorber) in the free space: a) EM wave transmission through a single absorber layer between two semi-infinite media; b) EM wave reflection from the absorber layer backed by a perfect electric conductor. d , ε^* , μ^* and Z_2 denote thickness, complex dielectric permittivity, complex magnetic permeability and characteristic impedance of the absorber layer. Z_1 and Z_3 are characteristic impedances of the semi-infinite media (air); Z_0 is a characteristic impedance of the free space.

In the first model of EM wave transmission (Fig. 6a), Eq. 3 can be transformed to

$$Z_{in} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu^*}{\varepsilon^*}} Z_0 \frac{1 + \sqrt{\frac{\mu^*}{\varepsilon^*}} \tanh(\gamma d)}{\sqrt{\frac{\mu^*}{\varepsilon^*}} + \tanh(\gamma d)} \quad (4)$$

Then reflection (ρ) and transmission (τ) coefficients can be defined [1,2,9] as following:

$$\rho = \frac{Z_{in} - Z_1}{Z_{in} + Z_1}, \quad (5)$$

$$\tau = \frac{2Z_{in}}{Z_{in} + Z_1}. \quad (6)$$

For practical reasons, we calculate frequency dependences of the modules of reflection (R), transmission (T) and absorption (A) coefficients in the logarithmic form:

$$R = 20 \log|\rho|, \quad T = 20 \log|\tau|, \quad A = 20 \log(1 - |\rho| - |\tau|). \quad (7)$$

The shielding efficiency SE is estimated as $SE = -T$.

In the second model of EM wave reflection (Fig. 6b), Eq. 3 can be transformed to

$$Z_{in} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu^*}{\varepsilon^*}} Z_0 \tanh(\gamma d). \quad (8)$$

Then frequency dependences of the the reflection loss (RL) and attenuation constant α (real part of the propagation constant γ) of the material, in nepers/m, can be calculated as following [2,8]:

$$RL = 20 \log|\rho| = 20 \log \left| \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\mu^*}{\varepsilon^*}} \tanh(\gamma d) - 1}{\sqrt{\frac{\mu^*}{\varepsilon^*}} \tanh(\gamma d) + 1} \right|, \quad (9)$$

$$\alpha = \text{Re}(\gamma) = \text{Re} \left(\frac{i\omega \sqrt{\mu^* \varepsilon^*}}{c} \right), \quad (10)$$

Reflection loss and attenuation constant characterize the MW absorption efficiency MA , which could be numerically estimated as $MA = -RL$.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 PET-CNT composites

We used experimental dielectric spectra of PET-CNT composites or their fits to Eqs. 1 and 2 shown in Fig. 1 to estimate the shielding efficiency and MW absorption in the MW and THz ranges by application of the algorithms described above (Section 3). The magnetic field effects were neglected in the quasi-static approximation and the value $\mu^* = 1 - i0$ was used in Equations (4, 8-10). Shielding and absorbing parameters were calculated in dependence on the CNT concentration, layer thickness ($d = 0.1 - 10$ mm) and frequency. Selected results are shown in Figs. 7-11.

First of all, let us note that dc conductivity does not determine the MW shielding properties of PET-CNT composites even above the percolation threshold, at least for $x < 0.6$ vol%. It is responsible only for the low-frequency plateaus of R -, T - and A - coefficients observed below 1 MHz (Fig. 7). The frequency dependent R -, T - and A - coefficients in MW and THz ranges are defined by the ac

conductivity, caused by dielectric relaxation. SE values up to 35 dB can be achieved at frequencies from 0.3 GHz to 500 GHz, depending on the CNT concentration x and layer thickness d . Increase of x and d results in the increase of SE and in the shift down of the high- SE frequency band corresponding to the broad minimum of T -coefficient (Figs. 7,8). The frequency band of high- SE is broad and achieves a decade of frequency at the 30 dB level, which is very important for the shielding applications.

Figure 7 (on the left): EM wave transmission through a single layer ($d = 1$ mm) of PET-CNT composites with different CNT concentration. Broad-band spectra of the (a) R -, (b) T -, (c) A -coefficients.

Figure 8 (on the right): EM wave transmission through a single layer ($d = 10$ mm) of PET-CNT composites with different CNT concentration. High-frequency, MW and THz spectra of the (a) R -, (b) T -, (c) A -coefficients.

For composites with high CNT concentration, $x > 0.75$ vol%, MW absorption is not effective because of their relatively high dc conductivity which results in the substantial reflection of the incident EM wave. As a result, the MA values do not exceed 10 dB for these compositions (Fig. 9). For the lower CNT concentration, MA values up to 30 dB can be achieved at frequencies from 2 GHz to 1000 GHz, depending on the CNT concentration and layer thickness. Increase of x and d results in the increase of MA and in the shift down of the high- MA frequency band corresponding to the relatively narrow minimum of the RL -coefficient (Fig. 9). The frequency bands of high- MA are narrow and multiple, different from the high- SE band, which is single and broad. The attenuation constant α reaches 100 neper/m in the GHz and 1000 neper/m in the THz ranges (Fig. 10). Increase of x results in the increase of α . High values of the attenuation constant are important for the absorbing applications of PET-CNT composites.

Analysis of the $SE(f,x,d)$ and $MA(f,x,d)$ dependences (Figs 7-10) simulated in a broad frequency range for different CNT concentrations and layer thicknesses allow us to define the compositions and frequency ranges suitable for shielding and absorbing applications. Composites with high CNT

concentration $x > 0.2$ vol%, i.e. above the percolation threshold, are suitable for the shielding applications. For the absorbing applications, the compositions with $x < 0.75$ vol%, i.e. both above and below the percolation threshold, can be used. The high-*SE* range can be expanded up to sub-THz frequencies at $x > 2$ vol% and down to sub-GHz frequencies at $x > 0.4$ vol%. The high-*MA* range can be expanded up to sub-THz frequencies at $x < 0.2$ vol%, and down to ~ 1 GHz at $0.2 < x < 0.75$ vol%.

Figure 9 (on the left): EM wave reflection from the layer of PET-CNT composites with different CNT concentration backed by a perfect electric conductor. MW and THz spectra of the reflection loss for the layer thickness (a) $d = 1$ mm and (b) $d = 10$ mm.

Figure 10 (on the right): EM wave reflection from the layer of PET-CNT composites with different CNT concentration backed by a perfect electric conductor. Broad-band spectra of the attenuation constant.

4.2 Epoxy-Ni and epoxy-Fe composites

In the case of epoxy-Fe and epoxy-Ni composites, not only their dielectric (Figs. 2 and 3), but also magnetic spectra (Figs. 4 and 5) were used for estimation of the shielding and absorption efficiency by Equations (6) – (12). The R -, T -, A - coefficients, reflection loss and attenuation constant were simulated in dependence on the metal concentration x , layer thickness ($d = 0.1 - 10$ mm) and frequency. Selected results are shown in Figs. 11-14.

The frequency dependent R -, T - and A - coefficients in high-frequency and MW ranges (Figs. 11, 12) are defined by both dielectric and magnetic parameters and their dispersion. For the epoxy-Fe composites, shielding efficiency $SE = -T$ values up to 40 dB can be obtained at frequencies from 0.3 GHz to 2 GHz. Increase of x and d results in the increase of SE and in the shift down of the high- SE frequency band corresponding to the broad minimum of T -coefficient. The frequency band of high- SE is broad and reaches a decade of frequency at the 30 dB level, which is very important for the shielding applications. The high- SE band of the epoxy-Ni composites is shifted toward high frequencies comparatively to the epoxy-Fe composite layers of the same metal concentration and thickness.

Figure 11 (on the left): EM wave transmission through a single layer ($d = 10$ mm) of epoxy-Fe composites with different Fe concentration. Spectra of the (a) R -, (b) T -, (c) A - coefficients.
Figure 12 (on the right): EM wave transmission through a single layer ($d = 3$ mm) of epoxy-Ni composites with different Ni concentration. Spectra of the (a) R -, (b) T -, (c) A - coefficients.

Figure 13 (on the left): EM wave reflection from the 10 mm thick layer of epoxy-Fe composites backed by a perfect electric conductor. Spectra of (a) reflection loss and (b) attenuation constant.
Figure 14 (on the right): EM wave reflection from the 3 mm thick layer of epoxy-Ni composites backed by a perfect electric conductor. Spectra of (a) reflection loss and (b) attenuation constant.

It is partially due to lower dielectric permittivity and loss of the epoxy-Ni composites (Figs. 2, 3), but mainly due to higher mean frequency of their magnetic permeability dispersion (Figs. 4, 5) which corresponds to the maximum of magnetic loss above 3 GHz, i.e. above our experimental range. Importance of the magnetic properties is clearly shown by comparison of curves “30” and “30 ($\mu^* = 1$)” in Fig. 11. Both curves correspond to the same composition ($x = 30$ vol% Fe) with the same dielectric parameters, but in the case of curve “30 ($\mu^* = 1$)” magnetic properties were neglected in calculations. Magnetic properties can contribute ~ 20 dB to the shielding efficiency.

Spectra of the reflection loss and attenuation constant (Figs. 13, 14) characterizing MW absorption are also defined by both dielectric and magnetic properties. For the epoxy-Ni composites, MW absorption $MA = -RL$ values up to 25 dB were achieved in the 1 - 3 GHz range. Variation of the metal content from 0 to 30 vol.% causes increase of the attenuation constant in more than 10 times at frequencies from 1 to 3 GHz up to the level of 100 nepers/m. High values of the attenuation constant is important for the absorbing applications of the epoxy-Fe/Ni composites. Increase of x and d results in the increase of MW absorption $MA = -RL$ and in the shift down of the high- MA frequency band corresponding to the minimum of reflection loss. The frequency band of high- MA is usually narrower than the high- SE one. Role of the magnetic properties can be estimated by comparison of curves “30” and “30 ($\mu^* = 1$)” in Figs. 13 and 14. Again, magnetic properties were neglected in calculations in the case of curve “30 ($\mu^* = 1$)”. Contribution of magnetic properties to the attenuation constant is dominant above 100 MHz: for composites with $x = 30$ vol%, neglect of the magnetic properties results in the decrease of α in 10 times. Magnetic properties provide broadening of the high- MA band and its shift toward lower frequencies, while increase of the MA values is not clear seen in the results of our calculations because of the absence of experimental magnetic spectra $\mu^*(f)$ above 3 GHz. Nevertheless, we can suppose essential magnetic contribution for the composite layers with $d < 3$ mm, especially for the epoxy-Ni composites when the layer geometrical resonance is combined with the maximum of magnetic losses above 3 GHz.

4.3 Variously conducting PANI

Phenomenological fits of PANI dielectric spectra [6] were used for calculations of shielding and absorption efficiency calculations of the nc-PANI, sc-PANI and c-PANI layers in dependence on the layer thickness ($d = 0.1 - 10$ mm) and frequency. The magnetic field effects were neglected, similar to the case of PET-CNT composites, and the value $\mu^* = 1 - i0$ was used in Equations (4, 8-10). Selected results are shown in Figs. 15 and 16.

Shielding efficiency of the nc-PANI, sc-PANI layers does not exceed 10 dB, while SE of the c-PANI layers can achieve 40 dB in a broad frequency band in the MW range (Fig. 15b). The 0.3 mm thin c-PANI layer provides the 20 dB SE band between 10 MHz and 50 GHz. Such a high level of shielding efficiency of the conductive PANI is mainly caused by the dc conductivity contribution.

MW absorption of the c-PANI layers is not effective because of their high dc conductivity which results in the substantial reflection of the incident EM wave. As a result, the MA values do not exceed 5 dB. For the nc-PANI and sc-PANI layers, MA values up to 20 dB can be achieved at frequencies from 10 GHz to 1 THz, depending on the layer thickness (Fig. 16a). The frequency bands of high- MA are narrow and multiple in the case of nc-PANI and sc-PANI, different from the single and broad high- SE band of the c-PANI layers. The attenuation constant α can be varied from 0.1 neper/m to 10 000 neper/m in the range of 0.1-100 GHz depending on the level of PANI dc conductivity (Fig. 16b). High values of the attenuation constant are important for the absorbing applications of PANI.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Studied dielectric-conductor nanocomposites were shown to be promising MW and THz shielding and absorbing materials. Their properties can be effectively controlled by changing the concentration of conductive fillers. PET-CNT composites are interesting for both shielding and absorbing applications. For the absorbing applications, low- x compositions ($0 < x < 0.75$ vol%) can be used; for the shielding ones, high- x compositions ($x > 0.2$ vol%) are preferable. Very low percolation threshold $x_c = 0.07$ vol% is an advantage for the applications.

Figure 15 (on the left): EM wave transmission through a single layer ($d = 0.3 \div 10$ mm) of the conducting PANI. Spectra of the (a) R -, (b) T -, (c) A - coefficients.

Figure 16 (on the right): EM wave reflection from the layer of PANI ($d = 0.3 \div 10$ mm) backed by a perfect electric conductor. Spectra of (a) reflection loss of the semiconducting PANI and (b) attenuation constant of variously conducting PANI.

Epoxy-Fe and epoxy-Ni composites can be used as microwave absorbing or shielding materials. Their shielding efficiency is higher than the absorption one. Magnetic properties of the Fe and Ni filler significantly contribute to the shielding and absorbing parameters. Variously conductive PANI show a high level of the shielding efficiency (c-PANI) or absorbing efficiency (sc-PANI and nc-PANI), depending on their dc conductivity level.

The broadband dielectric spectroscopy was shown to be an effective tool for study and development of microwave shielding and absorbing materials.

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